

1 Graphical Abstract

2 **MPMICE: A hybrid MPM-CFD model for simulating coupled prob-**
3 **lems in porous media. Application to earthquake-induced subma-**
4 **rine landslides**

5 Quoc Anh Tran, Gustav Grimstad, Seyed Ali Ghoreishian Amiri

soil-fluid-structure interaction

Application to earthquake-induced submarine landslide

6 Highlights

7 **MPMICE: A hybrid MPM-CFD model for simulating coupled prob-**
8 **lems in porous media. Application to earthquake-induced subma-**
9 **rine landslides**

10 Quoc Anh Tran, Gustav Grimstad, Seyed Ali Ghoreishian Amiri

- 11 • MPMICE is introduced for multiphase flow in porous media.
- 12 • Material Point method allows to model large deformation of non-isothermal
13 porous media.
- 14 • ICE (compressible multi-material CFD formulation) allows stabilizing
15 pore water pressure and turbulent flow.
- 16 • MPMICE is validated and apply to simulate the earthquake-induced
17 submarine landslide.

18 MPMICE: A hybrid MPM-CFD model for simulating
19 coupled problems in porous media. Application to
20 earthquake-induced submarine landslides

21 Quoc Anh Tran^a, Gustav Grimstad^a, Seyed Ali Ghoreishian Amiri^a

^a*Norwegian University of Science and Technology, , Trondheim, 7034, Norway*

22 **Abstract**

23 In this paper, we describe a soil-fluid-structure interaction model that com-
24 bines soil mechanics (saturated sediments), fluid mechanics (seawater or air),
25 and solid mechanics (structures). The formulation combines the Material
26 Point Method, which models large deformation of the porous media and the
27 structure, with the Implicit Continuous-fluid Eulerian, which models com-
28 plex fluid flows. We validate the model and simulate the whole process of
29 earthquake-induced submarine landslides. We show that this model captures
30 complex interactions between saturated sediment, seawater, and structure,
31 so we can use the model to estimate the impact of potential submarine land-
32 slides on offshore structures.

33 *Keywords:*

34 Material Point Method, MPMICE, submarine landslide.

35	Contents	
36	Nomenclature	4
37	Introduction	6
38	Theory and formulation	8
39	Assumptions	8
40	Governing equations	9
41	Constitutive soil model	11
42	Turbulent model	12
43	Frictional force for soil-structure interaction	12
44	Momentum and Energy exchange model	13
45	Solving momentum and energy exchange with an implicit solver	14
46	Equation of state for fluid phases	16
47	Numerical implementation	17
48	Interpolation from Solid Particle to Grid	18
49	Compute equation of state for fluid phase	20
50	Compute cell face velocity	20
51	Compute cell face temperature	21
52	Compute fluid pressure (implicit scheme)	22
53	Compute viscous shear stress term of the fluid phase	22
54	Compute nodal internal temperature of the solid phase	22
55	Compute and integrate acceleration of the solid phase	23
56	Compute Lagrangian value (mass, momentum and energy)	23
57	Compute Lagrangian specific volume of the fluid phase	24
58	Compute advection term and advance in time	25
59	Interpolate from cell to node of the solid phase	26
60	Update the particle variables	26
61	Numerical examples	27
62	Fluid Flow through isothermal porous media	27
63	Isothermal consolidation	28
64	Thermal induced cavity flow	29
65	Underwater debris flow	30
66	Validation of soil response to the seismic loading	34
67	Earthquake-induced submarine landslides	36

68	Conclusions	41
69	Acknowledgements	42
70	Appendix: Equation derivation	42
71	Evolution of porosity	42
72	Momentum conservation	43
73	Energy conservation	44
74	Advanced Fluid Pressure	45
75	Momentum and Energy exchange with an implicit solver	46

76 **Nomenclature**

General variables

<u>Variable</u>	<u>Dimensions</u>	<u>Description</u>
V	$[L^3]$	Representative volume
n		Porosity
$\boldsymbol{\sigma}$	$[ML^{-1}t^{-2}]$	Total stress tensor
Δt	$[t]$	Time increment
\mathbf{b}	$[ML^1t^{-2}]$	Body force
c_v	$[L^2t^{-2}T^{-1}]$	Constant volume specific heat
f_d	$[MLt^{-2}]$	Drag forces in momentum exchange term
f^{int}	$[MLt^{-2}]$	Internal forces
f^{ext}	$[MLt^{-2}]$	External forces
q_{fs}	$[MLt^{-2}]$	Heat exchange term
S		Weighting function
∇S		Gradient of weighting function

77

Solid phase

<u>Variable</u>	<u>Dimensions</u>	<u>Description</u>
m_s	$[M]$	Solid mass
ρ_s	$[ML^{-3}]$	Solid density
ϕ_s		Solid volume fraction
$\bar{\rho}_s$	$[ML^{-3}]$	Bulk Solid density
\mathbf{x}_s	$[L]$	Solid Position vector
\mathbf{U}_s	$[Lt^{-1}]$	Solid Velocity vector
\mathbf{a}_s	$[Lt^{-2}]$	Solid Acceleration vector
$\boldsymbol{\sigma}'$	$[ML^{-1}t^{-2}]$	Effective Stress tensor
$\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s$		Strain tensor
e_s	$[L^2t^{-2}]$	Solid Internal energy per unit mass
T_s	$[T]$	Solid Temperature
\mathbf{F}_s		Solid Deformation gradient
V_s	$[L^3]$	Solid Volume

Fluid phase

<u>Variable</u>	<u>Dimensions</u>	<u>Description</u>
m_f	$[M]$	Fluid mass
ρ_f	$[ML^{-3}]$	Fluid density
ϕ_f		Fluid volume fraction
$\bar{\rho}_f$	$[ML^{-3}]$	Bulk Fluid density
\mathbf{U}_f	$[Lt^{-1}]$	Fluid Velocity vector
$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_f$	$[ML^{-1}t^{-2}]$	Fluid stress tensor
p_f	$[ML^{-1}t^{-2}]$	Fluid isotropic pressure
$\boldsymbol{\tau}_f$	$[ML^{-1}t^{-2}]$	Fluid shear stress tensor
e_f	$[L^2t^{-2}]$	Fluid Internal energy per unit mass
T_f	$[T]$	Fluid Temperature
v_f	$[L^3/M]$	Fluid Specific volume $\frac{1}{\rho_f}$
α_f	$[1/T]$	Thermal expansion
μ	$[ML^{-1}t^{-1}]$	Fluid viscosity
V_f	$[L^3]$	Fluid Volume

78

Superscript

<u>Variable</u>	<u>Dimensions</u>	<u>Description</u>
n		Current time step
L		Lagrangian values
$n + 1$		Next time step

Subscript

c		Cell-centered quantity
p		Particle quantity
i		Node quantity
FC		Cell face quantity
L, R		Left and Right cell faces

79 **Introduction**

80 Many geological natural processes and their interactions with man-made
81 structures are influenced by soil-fluid-structure interactions. The predic-
82 tion of these processes requires a tool that can capture complex interactions
83 between soil, fluid, and structure, such as the process of submarine land-
84 slides. Indeed, The offshore infrastructure as well as coastal communities
85 may be vulnerable to submarine landslides. Submarine landslides contain
86 three stages: triggering, failure, and post-failure. Erosion or earthquakes can
87 trigger slope failures in the first stage. Following the failure, sediments move
88 quickly after the post-failure stage. In other words, solid-like sediments will
89 behave like a fluid after failure. This phase transition makes the simulation
90 of submarine landslides a challenging task.

91
92 Due to this phase transition, submarine landslide can be modeled by ei-
93 ther the Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) or the particle-based meth-
94 ods. For simulating submarine slides, CFD methods solve governing equa-
95 tions in a full-Eulerian framework [1, 2, 3, 4] with interface capturing tech-
96 niques. While CFD can handle complex flows (such as turbulent flows), it
97 cannot account for the triggering mechanism of submarine landslides because
98 it is not straightforward to consider 'soil constitutive laws' of sediment ma-
99 terials in the Eulerian framework. In contrast, particle-based methods can
100 overcome this problem by using the Lagrangian framework. These meth-
101 ods have been extensively used to simulate landslides, like Material Point
102 Method (MPM) [5], Smooth Particle Hydro Dynamics [6], Particle Finite
103 Element Method [7], or Coupled Eulerian Lagrangian Method [8]. For sim-
104 plicity, these simulations adopt total stress analysis which neglects the pore
105 pressure development which is key factor triggering slope failures.

106
107 Recent developments in particle-based methods model the coupling of
108 fluid flows in porous media by sets of Lagrangian particles. For the MPM
109 family, it is the double-point MPM ([9, 10, 11]) where fluid particles and
110 solid particles are overlapped in a single computational grid. Even if fluid
111 flows are considered, particle-based methods have numerical instability in
112 modeling the fluid flow, which requires additional numerical treatments such
113 as the B-bar method [9], null-space filter [12], or least square approximation
114 [13, 14]. Indeed, CFD is a more optimal option for complex fluid flows
115 especially dealing with large distortions of continuum fluid media. Therefore,

116 it could be ideal to combine the CFD with particle-based methods. More than
 117 50 particle-based methods have been developed to solve large deformations
 118 of solids over the last two decades [15], but the MPM appears to be the
 119 best candidate for coupling with the CFD. Because MPM incorporates a
 120 stationary mesh during computation, just like CFD. As such, both MPM
 121 and CFD can be coupled naturally in a unified computational mesh.

Figure 1: Interaction between soil-fluid-structure

122

Figure 2: Coupling of soil-water-structure interaction using MPMICE

123 A numerical method for simulating soil-fluid-structure interaction (Figure
124 1) involving large deformations, is presented in this work in order to simu-
125 late the interaction between sediment (soil), seawater (fluid) and offshore
126 structures (structure) namely MPMICE (Figure 2). In the MPMICE, the
127 Material Point Method (MPM) is coupled with the Implicit Continuous Eu-
128 lerian (ICE). The MPM method is a particle method that allows the porous
129 soil to undergo arbitrary distortions. The ICE method, on the other hand,
130 is a conservative finite volume technique with all state variables located at
131 the cell center (temperature, velocity, mass, pressure). An initial technical
132 report [16] at Los Alamos National Laboratory provided the theoretical and
133 algorithmic foundation for the MPMICE, followed by the MPMICE devel-
134 opment and implementation in the high-performance Uintah computational
135 framework for simulating fluid-structure interactions [17]. This paper pri-
136 marily contributes further to the development of the MPMICE for analyzing
137 the **soil**-fluid-structure interaction, since sediment should be considered as a
138 porous media (soil) and not as a solid to capture the evolution of the pore
139 water pressure. Baumgarten et al. [18] made the first attempt at coupling
140 the Finite Volume Method with the MPM for the simulation of soil-fluid
141 interaction. In contrast to the mentioned work, we use implicit time inte-
142 gration for the multi phase flows instead of explicit time integration for the
143 single-phase flow.

144 **Theory and formulation**

145 This section lay out the theoretical framework for the MPMICE model.
146 We use the common notation of the continuum mechanics with vector and
147 tensor denoted simply by using bold font and scalar denoted by using normal
148 font. The notation are shown in Nomenclature.

149 *Assumptions*

150 The following assumptions are made for the MPMICE model.

- 151 1. Solid phases (MPM) are described in a Lagrangian formulation while
152 fluid phases (ICE) are described in an Eulerian formulation in the
153 framework of continuum mechanics and mixture theory.
- 154 2. Solid grains are incompressible while the fluid phases are compressible.
155 Solid's thermal expansion is negligible.
- 156 3. There is no mass exchange between solid and fluid phases.
- 157 4. Terzaghi's effective stress is valid.

158 *Governing equations*

159 A representative element volume Ω is decomposed by two domains: solid
 160 domains Ω_s and fluid domains Ω_f . Then, all domains are homogenized
 161 into two overlapping continua. Considering the volume fraction of solid
 162 $\phi_s = \Omega_s/\Omega$ and fluid $\phi_f = \Omega_f/\Omega$ with the true (or Eulerian) porosity
 163 $n = \sum \phi_f$ of the representative element volume, the average density of solid
 164 and fluid phases are defined as:

$$165 \quad \bar{\rho}_s = \phi_s \rho_s, \quad \bar{\rho}_f = \phi_f \rho_f \quad (1)$$

166 The mass of solid and fluid phases are:

$$167 \quad m_s = \int_{\Omega_s} \rho_s dV = \bar{\rho}_s V, \quad m_f = \int_{\Omega_f} \rho_f dV = \bar{\rho}_f V \quad (2)$$

168 Reviewing the Terzaghi's effective stress concept for the saturated porous
 169 media, the total stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is calculated by:

$$170 \quad \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}' - p_f \mathbf{I} \quad (3)$$

171 The balance equations are derived based on the mixture theory. The rep-
 172 resentative thermodynamic state of the fluid phases are given by the vector
 173 $[m_f, \mathbf{U}_f, e_f, T_f, v_f]$ which are mass, velocity, internal energy, temperature,
 174 specific volume. The representative state of the solid phases are given by the
 175 vector $[m_s, \mathbf{U}_s, e_s, T_s, \boldsymbol{\sigma}', p_f]$ which are mass, velocity, internal energy, temper-
 176 ature, effective stress and pore water pressure. The derivation is presented
 177 in detail in the Appendix.

178

179 Mass Conservation

180 The mass balance equations for both fluid (e.g., water, air) and solid phases
 181 are:

$$182 \quad \frac{1}{V} \frac{\partial m_f}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (m_f \mathbf{U}_f) = 0, \quad \frac{1}{V} \frac{D_s m_s}{Dt} = 0 \quad (4)$$

183 Solving the mass balance equation of the solid phase leads to:

$$\frac{D_s n}{Dt} = \phi_s \nabla \cdot \mathbf{U}_s \quad (5)$$

184

185 Momentum Conservation

186 The momentum balance equations for the fluid phases (e.g., water, air) are:

$$\frac{1}{V} \left[\frac{\partial(m_f \mathbf{U}_f)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (m_f \mathbf{U}_f \mathbf{U}_f) \right] = -\phi_f \nabla p_f + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_f + \bar{\rho}_f \mathbf{b} + \sum \mathbf{f}_d \quad (6)$$

187 The momentum balance equations for the solid phases are:

$$\frac{1}{V} \frac{D_s(m_s \mathbf{U}_s)}{Dt} = \nabla \cdot (\boldsymbol{\sigma}') - \phi_s \nabla p_f + \bar{\rho}_s \mathbf{b} + \sum \mathbf{f}_{fric} - \sum \mathbf{f}_d \quad (7)$$

188

189 Energy Conservation

190 The internal energy balance equations for the fluid phases (e.g., water, air)
191 are:

$$\frac{1}{V} \left[\frac{\partial(m_f e_f)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (m_f e_f \mathbf{U}_f) \right] = -\bar{\rho}_f p_f \frac{D_f v_f}{Dt} + \boldsymbol{\tau}_f : \nabla \mathbf{U}_f + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q}_f + \sum q_{sf} \quad (8)$$

192 The internal energy balance equations for the solid phase are:

$$\frac{m_s}{V} c_v \frac{D_s(T_s)}{Dt} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}' : \frac{D_s(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}'_s)}{Dt} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q}_s - \sum q_{sf} \quad (9)$$

193 where c_v is the specific heat at constant volume of the solid materials.

194

195 Closing the systems of equations, the following additional models are needed:

- 196 (1) A constitutive equation to describe the stress - strain behaviour of solid
197 phase (computing effective stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}'$).
- 198 (2) Optional turbulent model to compute the viscous shear stress $\boldsymbol{\tau}_f$.
- 199 (3) Frictional forces \mathbf{f}_{fric} for the contact for soil-structure interaction be-
200 tween solid/porous materials with the friction coefficient μ_{fric} .
- 201 (4) Exchange momentum models (computing drag force \mathbf{f}_d) for interaction
202 between materials.
- 203 (5) Energy exchange models (computing temperature exchange term q_{sf}) for
204 interaction between materials.
- 205 (6) An equation of state to establish relations between thermodynamics vari-
206 ables of each fluid materials $[P_f, \bar{\rho}_f, v_f, T_f, e_f]$.

207 Four thermodynamic relations for the equation of states are:

$$\begin{aligned}
e_f &= e_f(T_f, v_f) \\
P_f &= P_f(T_f, v_f) \\
\phi_f &= v_f \bar{\rho}_f \\
0 &= n - \sum_{f=1}^{N_f} v_f \bar{\rho}_f
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

208 *Constitutive soil model*

209 As a result of the explicit MPM formulation, we can derive the consti-
210 tutive law in the updated Lagrangian framework of "small strain - large
211 deformation". Therefore, the rotation of the particles (representative ele-
212 ment volume) is manipulated by rotating the Cauchy stress tensor. First,
213 the deformation gradient is decomposed into the polar rotation tensor \mathbf{R}_s^{n+1}
214 and stretch tensor \mathbf{V}_s^{n+1} as:

$$\mathbf{F}_s^{n+1} = \mathbf{V}_s^{n+1} \mathbf{R}_s^{n+1} \tag{11}$$

215 Then, before calling the constitutive model, the stress and strain rate tensor
216 are rotated to the reference configuration as:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}'^{,n*} = (\mathbf{R}_s^{n+1})^T \boldsymbol{\sigma}'^{,n} \mathbf{R}_s^{n+1} \tag{12}$$

217

$$\delta \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{n*} = (\mathbf{R}_s^{n+1})^T \delta \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^n \mathbf{R}_s^{n+1} \tag{13}$$

218 Using the constitutive model with the input tensors $\boldsymbol{\sigma}'^{,n*}, \delta \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{n*}$ to compute
219 the Cauchy stress tensor at the advanced time step $\boldsymbol{\sigma}'^{,n+1*}$ then rotating it
220 back to current configuration as:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}'^{,n+1} = \mathbf{R}_s^{n+1} \boldsymbol{\sigma}'^{,n+1*} (\mathbf{R}_s^{n+1})^T \tag{14}$$

221 In this paper, we adopt the hyper-elastic Neo Hookean model for the structure
222 materials and additionally Mohr-Coulomb failure criteria for the soil (porous
223 media) materials. The Cauchy stress of the hyper-elastic Neo Hookean model
224 can be written as:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}' = \frac{\lambda \ln(J)}{J} + \frac{\mu}{J} (\mathbf{F} \mathbf{F}^T - \mathbf{J}) \tag{15}$$

225 where λ and μ are bulk and shear modulus and J is the determinant of the
226 deformation gradient \mathbf{F} . And the yield function f and flow potentials g of

227 the Mohr-Coulomb can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} f &= -\sigma'_1 + \sigma'_3 + 2c' \cos(\phi') + (\sigma'_1 + \sigma'_3) \sin(\phi') \\ g &= -\sigma'_1 + \sigma'_3 + 2c' \cos(\psi') + (\sigma'_1 + \sigma'_3) \sin(\psi') \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

228 In the equations, c' , ϕ' , and ψ' represent the cohesion, friction angle, and
 229 dilation angle, respectively. σ'_1 and σ'_3 denote the maximum and minimum
 230 principal stresses, with the condition $\sigma'_1 < \sigma'_3 < 0$. It is important to note
 231 that in our assumptions, stress is considered positive during extension, which
 232 means the signs of the stresses in these equations are opposite to those in
 233 standard Soil Mechanic's textbooks.

234 *Turbulent model*

235 The turbulent effect is modelled using a statistical approach namely large-
 236 eddy simulation. In this approach, the micro-scale turbulent influence in the
 237 dynamics of the macro-scale motion is computed through simple models like
 238 Smagorinsky model. In the Smagorinsky model, the residual stress tensor is:

$$\tau_{ij} = 2\mu_{eff}(\bar{S}_{ij} - \frac{1}{3}\delta_{ij}\bar{S}_{kk}) + \frac{1}{3}\delta_{ij}\tau_{kk} \quad (17)$$

239 where the the strain rate tensor is given by:

$$\bar{S}_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\delta \bar{U}_i}{\delta x_j} + \frac{\delta \bar{U}_j}{\delta x_i} \right) \quad (18)$$

240 and the effective viscosity is sum of molecular viscosity and turbulent viscos-
 241 ity $\mu_{eff} = \mu + \mu_t$ in which the turbulent viscosity μ_t is calculated by:

$$\mu_t = (C_s \Delta)^2 \sqrt{2\bar{S}_{ij}\bar{S}_{ij}} \quad (19)$$

242 where C_s is the Smagorinsky constant with the value of 0.1 and $\Delta = \sqrt[3]{dxdydz}$
 243 is the grid size that defines the subgrid length scale.

244 *Frictional force for soil-structure interaction*

245 MPMICE includes a contact law for the interaction between soil and
 246 structure using the first Coulomb friction contact for MPM presented by
 247 Bardenhagen et al. ([19]). The magnitude of the friction force at the contact
 248 depends on the friction coefficient μ_{fric} and the normal force \mathbf{f}_{norm} computed
 249 from the projection of the contact force in the normal direction.

$$\mathbf{f}_{fric} = \mu_{fric} \mathbf{f}_{norm} \quad (20)$$

250 The contact determines whether the soil is sliding or sticking to the structure
 251 by comparing the friction force with the sticking force \mathbf{f}_{stick} computed from
 252 the projection of the contact force in the tangent direction as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{if } \mathbf{f}_{fric} \geq \mathbf{f}_{stick} \text{ no sliding} \\ & \text{if } \mathbf{f}_{fric} < \mathbf{f}_{stick} \text{ sliding occurs} \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

253 Frictional sliding between solid materials also generates dissipation and the
 254 work rate generated from the sliding can be calculated as:

$$\Delta W_{friction} = \mathbf{f}_{fric} d \quad (22)$$

255 where d is the sliding distance which can be computed based on the sliding
 256 velocity between two materials.

257 *Momentum and Energy exchange model*

258 Currently, the energy exchange coefficient H_{sf} is assumed to be constant
 259 for the sake of simplicity. Then the energy exchange can be written as:

$$q_{sf} = H_{sf}(T_f - T_s) \quad (23)$$

260 On the other hand, the drag force can be calculated as:

$$\mathbf{f}_d = K(\mathbf{U}_s - \mathbf{U}_f) \quad (24)$$

261 For the momentum exchange between fluid flows and porous media, we as-
 262 sume that the drag force \mathbf{f}_d depends on the average grain size of the grains
 263 D_p , the porosity n , the fluid viscosity μ_f , and is proportional to the relative
 264 velocities of soil grains and fluid ($\mathbf{U}_s - \mathbf{U}_f$). Based on recent investigation
 265 of CFD simulations of fluid flow around mono- and bi-disperse packing of
 266 spheres for $0.1 < \phi_s < 0.6$ and $Re < 1000$ [20]. The drag force is given by:

$$\mathbf{f}_d = \frac{18\phi_s(1 - \phi_s)\mu_f}{D_p^2} F(\phi_s, Re)(\mathbf{U}_s - \mathbf{U}_f) \quad (25)$$

268 where Reynolds number Re are computed as:

$$Re = \frac{n\rho_f D_p}{\mu_f} \|(\mathbf{U}_s - \mathbf{U}_f)\| \quad (26)$$

269 The function $F(\phi_s, Re)$ can be calculated as:

$$F(\phi_s, Re) = F(\phi_s, 0) + \frac{0.413Re}{24(1 - \phi_s)^2} \left(\frac{(1 - \phi_s)^{-1} + 3\phi_s(1 - \phi_s) + 8.4Re^{-0.343}}{1 + 10^3\phi_s Re^{-(1+4\phi_s)/2}} \right) \quad (27)$$

270 where the low Reynold coefficient $F(\phi_s, Re \rightarrow 0)$ is:

$$F(\phi_s, 0) = \frac{10\phi_s}{(1 - \phi_s)^2} + (1 - \phi_s)^2(1 + 1.5\sqrt{\phi_s}) \quad (28)$$

271 When validating the model with analytical solution, it requires to know the
 272 hydraulic conductivity K . In such case, we convert the equation (25) to
 273 Kozeny-Carman formula by assuming $F(\phi_s, Re) = 10\phi_s/(1 - \phi_s)^2$, leading to

$$\mathbf{f}_d = \frac{180\phi_s^2\mu_f}{D_p^2(1 - \phi_s)}(\mathbf{U}_s - \mathbf{U}_f) \quad (29)$$

274 Then, the dragging force following the Darcy law is given by:

$$\mathbf{f}_d = \frac{n^2\mu_f}{\kappa}(\mathbf{U}_s - \mathbf{U}_f) \quad (30)$$

275 where κ being intrinsic permeability of soil which can be written as:

$$\kappa = \frac{K\mu_f}{\rho_f g} \quad (31)$$

276 As such, the hydraulic conductivity will be expressed as:

$$K = \frac{D_p^2(1 - \phi_s)^3}{180\phi_s^2\mu_f}\rho_f g \quad (32)$$

277 *Solving momentum and energy exchange with an implicit solver*

278 The derivation of the implicit integration for the momentum exchange is
 279 presented in the Appendix's section 'Momentum and energy exchange with
 280 an implicit solver'. The linear equations for multi phases $i,j=1:N$ has the
 281 form as:

$$\begin{vmatrix} (1 + \beta_{ij}) & -\beta_{ij} \\ -\beta_{ji} & (1 + \beta_{ji}) \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} \Delta\mathbf{U}_i \\ \Delta\mathbf{U}_j \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} \beta_{ij}(\mathbf{U}_i^* - \mathbf{U}_j^*) \\ \beta_{ji}(\mathbf{U}_i^* - \mathbf{U}_j^*) \end{vmatrix}$$

Figure 3: Momentum exchange coefficient between materials

282 where the intermediate velocity for fluid phases $f=1:N_f$ and for solid/porous
 283 phases $s=1:N_s$ can be calculated by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{U}_f^* &= \mathbf{U}_f^n + \Delta t \left(-\frac{\nabla P_f^{n+1}}{\rho_f^n} + \frac{\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_f^n}{\bar{\rho}_f^n} + \mathbf{b} \right) \\
 \mathbf{U}_s^* &= \mathbf{U}_s^n + \Delta t \left(\frac{\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}'^n}{\bar{\rho}_s^n} - \frac{\nabla P_f^{n+1}}{\rho_s} + \mathbf{b} \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{33}$$

284 Also, the momentum exchange coefficient can be computed at every time
 285 step as $\beta_{12} = K/\bar{\rho}_f^n$ and $\beta_{21} = K/\bar{\rho}_s^n$ with the coefficient depending on the
 286 different type of interactions (see Figure 3) as for example:

287

- 288 1. The drag force is set to zero in soil-structure interactions, and instead
 289 the frictional force is computed.
- 290 2. As a result of fluid-structure interaction, the momentum exchange coef-
 291 ficient should be extremely high (1E15) when the solid material points
 292 are considered to be zero-porosity/zero-permeability.
- 293 3. In the case of soil-fluid interaction, the drag force is calculated using
 294 the equation (25). Considering that air has a much lower viscosity than

295 water, its drag force is much lower than the drag force of water in a
 296 pore.

297 4. A momentum exchange coefficient of 1E5 is applied between multiphase
 298 flows. This value is far higher than reality [21], but it is necessary to
 299 have enough numerical stability to conduct simulations in the numerical
 300 example.

301 Similar approach applied for the energy exchange term leading to:

$$\begin{vmatrix} (1 + \eta_{ij}) & -\eta_{ij} \\ -\eta_{ji} & (1 + \eta_{ji}) \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} \Delta T_i \\ \Delta T_j \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} \eta_{ij}(T_i^n - T_j^n) \\ \eta_{ji}(T_j^n - T_i^n) \end{vmatrix}$$

302 with η being the energy exchange coefficient.

303 *Equation of state for fluid phases*

Figure 4: Equation of state of water

304 The equation of state establishes relations between thermodynamics vari-
 305 ables $[P_f, \rho_f, T_f]$. The choice of the equation of state depends on the types
 306 of the fluid materials. For example, for the air, it is possible to assume the
 307 equation of state for the perfect gas which obeys:

$$P_f = \rho_f RT_f \tag{34}$$

308 where R is the gas constant. For the water, a simple linear equation of state
 309 is in the following form:

$$P_f = P_{ref} + K_f(\rho_f - \rho_{ref} + \alpha_f(T_f - T_{ref})) \quad (35)$$

310 where reference pressure $P_{ref} = 1 \text{ atm} = 101325 \text{ Pa}$, reference temperature
 311 $T_{ref} = 10^\circ\text{C}$, reference density $\rho_{ref} = 999.8 \text{ kg/m}^3$, the bulk modulus of water
 312 $K_f = 2 \text{ GPa}$, and the water thermal expansion $\alpha_f = 0.18 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$. Equation
 313 (35) matches well with the state of the water (see Figure 4).

314 Numerical implementation

Figure 5: GIMP weighting function (red as a convolution of the linear basis shape function (green) and the characteristic function (blue))

315 The fluid phases are discretized in the grid with the state variables stored
 316 at the centroid of the cells $[\rho_{f,c}, \mathbf{U}_{f,c}, T_{f,c}, v_{f,c}]$ while the solid phase is dis-
 317 cretized in the particles with the state variables $[m_{sp}, \mathbf{U}_{sp}, T_{sp}, \boldsymbol{\sigma}'_{sp}]$. In the
 318 Material Point Method, we use the generalized interpolation technique [22]
 319 using the weight function as a convolution of a grid shape function $N_i(\mathbf{x})$ in

320 a nodal domain Ω_i and a characteristic function $\chi_p(\mathbf{x})$ in a particle domain
 321 Ω_p with the volume $V_p(\mathbf{x})$ as follows:

$$S_{ip} = \frac{1}{V_p} \int_{\Omega_i \cap \Omega_p} N_i(\mathbf{x}) \chi_p(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} \quad (36)$$

322 where the volume $V_p(\mathbf{x})$ of the material point p can be calculated as:

$$V_p = \int_{\Omega_p} \chi_p(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} \quad (37)$$

323 The characteristic function is the Heaviside function as $\chi_p = 1$ if $\mathbf{x} \in \Omega_p$,
 324 otherwise 0 (see Figure 5). For the interpolation of the centroid of the cell,
 325 the linear basis function is used as:

$$S_{ci} = N_i(\mathbf{x}_c) \quad (38)$$

326 The time discretization are solved using the following steps.

327 *Interpolation from Solid Particle to Grid*

328 The nodal values of the solid state (mass, velocity, temperature, volume)
 329 are:

$$\begin{aligned} m_{si}^n &= \sum S_{ip} m_{sp} \\ \mathbf{U}_{si}^n &= \frac{\sum S_{ip} (m\mathbf{U})_{sp}^n}{m_{si}^n} \\ T_{si}^n &= \frac{\sum S_{ip} (mT)_{sp}^n}{m_{si}^n} \\ V_{si}^n &= \frac{\sum S_{ip} (mV)_{sp}^n}{m_{si}^n} \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{si}^n &= \frac{\sum S_{ip} (\boldsymbol{\sigma}V)_{sp}^n}{V_{si}^n} \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

330 The nodal internal forces is calculated by:

$$\mathbf{f}_{si}^{int,n} = - \sum \nabla S_{ip} (\boldsymbol{\sigma}'_{sp})^n V_{sp}^n \quad (40)$$

331 The nodal external forces $\mathbf{f}_{si}^{ext,n}$ and the frictional forces from soil-structure
 332 interaction $\mathbf{f}_{fric,si}^n$ from contact between materials are computed here.

Figure 6: Numerical implementation of MPMICE

333 Then we compute the solid cell variables as:

$$\begin{aligned}
m_{sc}^n &= \sum S_{ci} m_{si} \\
\rho_{sc}^n &= \frac{m_{sc}^n}{V} \\
\mathbf{U}_{sc}^n &= \sum S_{ci} \mathbf{U}_{si}^n \\
T_{sc}^n &= \sum S_{ci} T_{si}^n \\
V_{sc}^n &= \sum S_{ci} V_{si}^n \\
\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{sc}^n &= \sum S_{ci} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{si}^n
\end{aligned} \tag{41}$$

334 *Compute equation of state for fluid phase*

335 The total fluid material volume of a cell is:

$$V_{total} = \sum_{f=1}^{N_f} M_f v_f \tag{42}$$

336 We need to find $P_{f,c}^n$ which allows each fluid materials obey their equation of
337 states $[P_f, \rho_f, v_f, T_f, e_f]$ but also allow mass of all fluid materials to fill the
338 entire the pore volume without ongoing compression or expansion following
339 the condition as follows:

$$0 = n - \sum_{f=1}^{N_f} v_f \bar{\rho}_f \tag{43}$$

340 Then, we can use the Newton-Raphson iteration to find the value of $P_{f,c}^n$
341 which satisfies the equation (42, 43) and each equation of states of each fluid
342 materials.

343 *Compute cell face velocity*

344 Following the derivation in the Appendix: Advanced Fluid Pressure, we
345 first compute the fluid cell face velocity as:

$$\mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^{L-} = \frac{(\bar{\rho}\mathbf{U})_{f,FC}^n}{\bar{\rho}_{f,FC}^n} + \Delta t \left(-\frac{\nabla^{FC} P_{f,c}^n}{\rho_{f,FC}^n} + \frac{\nabla^{FC} \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}^n}{\bar{\rho}_{s,FC}} + \mathbf{b} \right) \tag{44}$$

346 The equation (44) is discretized in three dimension (noted that $\nabla^{FC} \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} = 0$),
347 for example the discretized equation in the x direction is:

$$U_{fx}^{L-} = \frac{(\bar{\rho}U)_{fx,R}^n + (\bar{\rho}U)_{fx,L}^n}{\bar{\rho}_{fx,L}^n + \bar{\rho}_{fx,R}^n} + \Delta t \left(-\frac{2(v_{fx,L}^n v_{fx,R}^n) P_{f,cx,R}^n - P_{f,cx,L}^n}{v_{fx,L}^n + v_{fx,R}^n} \frac{1}{\Delta x} + b_x \right) \tag{45}$$

348 The cell face solid velocity can be calculated as:

$$\mathbf{U}_{s,FC}^{L-} = \frac{(\bar{\rho}\mathbf{U})_{s,FC}^n}{\bar{\rho}_{s,FC}^n} + \Delta t \left(\frac{\nabla^{FC} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}'_c}{\bar{\rho}_{s,FC}} - \frac{\nabla^{FC} P_{f,c}^n}{\rho_s} + \mathbf{b} \right) \quad (46)$$

349 The equation (46) is discretized in three dimension (noted that $\nabla^{FC} \cdot \sigma_{ij} = 0$
350 with $i \neq j$), for example the discretized equation in the x direction is:

$$U_{sx}^{L-} = \frac{(\bar{\rho}U)_{sx,R}^n + (\bar{\rho}U)_{sx,L}^n}{\bar{\rho}_{sx,L}^n + \bar{\rho}_{sx,R}^n} + \Delta t \left(\frac{2(\sigma_{xx,R} - \sigma_{xx,L})}{(\bar{\rho}_{sx,L}^n + \bar{\rho}_{sx,R}^n)\Delta x} - \frac{P_{f,cx,R}^n - P_{f,cx,L}^n}{\rho_s \Delta x} + b_x \right) \quad (47)$$

351 Then, we compute the modified cell face velocity \mathbf{U}_{FC}^L considering the mo-
352 mentum exchange (see the Appendix: Momentum exchange with an implicit
353 solve) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^L &= \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^{L-} + \Delta \mathbf{U}_{f,FC} \\ \mathbf{U}_{s,FC}^L &= \mathbf{U}_{s,FC}^{L-} + \Delta \mathbf{U}_{s,FC} \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

354 The linear equation below is solved to obtain the increment of velocity with
355 $i, j = 1 : N$ as:

$$\begin{vmatrix} (1 + \beta_{ij}) & -\beta_{ij} \\ -\beta_{ji} & (1 + \beta_{ji}) \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} \Delta \mathbf{U}_{i,FC} \\ \Delta \mathbf{U}_{j,FC} \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} \beta_{ij}(\mathbf{U}_{i,FC}^{L-} - \mathbf{U}_{j,FC}^{L-}) \\ \beta_{ji}(\mathbf{U}_{j,FC}^{L-} - \mathbf{U}_{i,FC}^{L-}) \end{vmatrix}$$

356 *Compute cell face temperature*

357 Similar to the velocity, the faced temperature is computed, for example
358 in x direction, as:

$$\begin{aligned} T_{fx}^{L-} &= \frac{(\bar{\rho}T)_{fx,R}^n + (\bar{\rho}T)_{fx,L}^n}{\bar{\rho}_{fx,L}^n + \bar{\rho}_{fx,R}^n} \\ T_{sx}^{L-} &= \frac{(\bar{\rho}T)_{sx,R}^n + (\bar{\rho}T)_{sx,L}^n}{\bar{\rho}_{sx,L}^n + \bar{\rho}_{sx,R}^n} \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

359 Then, we compute the modified cell face temperature T_{FC}^L considering the
360 energy exchange (see the Appendix: Momentum and energy exchange with
361 an implicit solver) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} T_{f,FC}^L &= T_{f,FC}^{L-} + \Delta T_{f,FC} \\ T_{s,FC}^L &= T_{s,FC}^{L-} + \Delta T_{s,FC} \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

362 The linear equation below is solved to determine the increment of velocity
363 with $i, j = 1 : N$ as:

$$\begin{vmatrix} (1 + \eta_{ij}) & -\eta_{ij} \\ -\eta_{ji} & (1 + \eta_{ji}) \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} \Delta T_{i,FC} \\ \Delta T_{j,FC} \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} \eta_{ij}(T_{i,FC}^{L-} - T_{j,FC}^{L-}) \\ \eta_{ji}(T_{j,FC}^{L-} - T_{i,FC}^{L-}) \end{vmatrix}$$

364 *Compute fluid pressure (implicit scheme)*

365 For single phase flow, the increment of the fluid pressure can be computed
366 as:

$$\kappa_f \frac{\Delta P}{dt} = \nabla^c \cdot \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^{n+1} \quad (51)$$

367 For multi-phase flows, the increment of the fluid pressure of the mixture can
368 be computed as:

$$\kappa \frac{\Delta P}{dt} = \sum_{f=1}^{N_f} \nabla^c \cdot (\phi_{f,FC} \mathbf{U}_{f,FC})^{n+1} \quad (52)$$

369 where $\kappa = \sum_{f=1}^{N_f} (\phi_{f,FC} \kappa_f) / \sum_{f=1}^{N_f} (\phi_{f,FC})$. Then, the fluid pressure at cell
370 center is:

$$P_c^{n+1} = P_c^n + \Delta P_c^n \quad (53)$$

371 Finally, the cell face advanced fluid pressure is:

$$P_{FC}^{n+1} = \left(\frac{P_{c,L}^{n+1}}{\bar{\rho}_{f,L}^n} + \frac{P_{c,R}^{n+1}}{\bar{\rho}_{f,R}^n} \right) / \left(\frac{1}{\bar{\rho}_{f,L}^n} + \frac{1}{\bar{\rho}_{f,R}^n} \right) = \left(\frac{P_{c,L}^{n+1} \bar{\rho}_{f,R}^n + P_{c,R}^{n+1} \bar{\rho}_{f,L}^n}{\bar{\rho}_{f,L}^n \bar{\rho}_{f,R}^n} \right) \quad (54)$$

372 *Compute viscous shear stress term of the fluid phase*

373 This part compute the viscous shear stress $\Delta(m\mathbf{U})_{f,c,\tau}$ for a single vis-
374 cous compressible Newtonian fluid and optionally shear stress induced by the
375 turbulent model.

376 *Compute nodal internal temperature of the solid phase*

377 The nodal internal temperature rate is computed based on the heat con-
378 duction model as below:

$$dT_{si}^{L-} = \frac{(\Delta W_{si}^n + \Delta W_{fric,i}^n + \nabla^i \cdot \mathbf{q}_{si}^n)}{m_{si}^n c_v} \quad (55)$$

379 where $\Delta W_{si}^n = \boldsymbol{\sigma}' : \frac{D_s(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^p)}{Dt}$ is the mechanical work rate computed from the
380 constitutive model with $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^p$ is the plastic strain, $\Delta W_{fric,i}^n$ is the work rate
381 computed from the contact law due to the frictional sliding between solid
382 materials. The heat flux is $\mathbf{q}_s = \bar{\rho}_s \beta_s \nabla T_s$ with β_s being the thermal conduc-
383 tivity of the solid materials.

$$T_{si}^{L-} = T_{si}^n + dT_{si}^{L-} \quad (56)$$

384 *Compute and integrate acceleration of the solid phase*

385 After interpolating from material points to the nodes, the nodal acceler-
 386 ation and velocity are calculated by:

$$\mathbf{a}_{si}^{L-} = \frac{\mathbf{f}_{si}^{int,n} + \mathbf{f}_{si}^{ext,n}}{m_{si}^n} + \mathbf{g} \quad (57)$$

387

$$\mathbf{U}_{si}^{L-} = \mathbf{U}_{si}^n + \mathbf{a}_{si}^{L-} \Delta t \quad (58)$$

388 *Compute Lagrangian value (mass, momentum and energy)*

389 For the fluid phase, the linear momentum rate, the energy rate are:

$$\Delta(m\mathbf{U})_{f,c} = V n_c^n \nabla^c P_c^{n+1} + \Delta(m\mathbf{U})_{f,c,\tau} + V \bar{\rho}_{f,c}^n g \quad (59)$$

390

$$\Delta(me)_{f,c} = V n_c^n P_c^{n+1} \nabla^c \cdot \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^* + \nabla^c \cdot \mathbf{q}_{f,c}^n \quad (60)$$

391 The Lagrangian value of the mass, linear momentum and energy of fluid
 392 phases without momentum exchange are:

$$m_{f,c}^L = V \bar{\rho}_{f,c}^n \quad (61)$$

393

$$(m\mathbf{U})_{f,c}^{L-} = V \bar{\rho}_{f,c}^n \mathbf{U}_{f,c}^n + \Delta(m\mathbf{U})_{f,c} \quad (62)$$

394

$$(me)_{f,c}^{L-} = V \bar{\rho}_{f,c}^n T_{f,c}^n c_v + \Delta(me)_{f,c} \quad (63)$$

395 For the solid phase, the Lagrangian value of the linear momentum and energy
 396 of solid phase are:

$$m_{sc}^L = m_{sc}^n \quad (64)$$

397

$$(m\mathbf{U})_{sc}^{L-} = \sum S_{ci} m_{si}^n \mathbf{U}_{si}^{L-} + V(1 - n_c^n) \nabla^c P_{f,c}^{n+1} \quad (65)$$

398

$$(me)_{sc}^{L-} = \sum S_{ci} m_{si}^n T_{si}^L c_v \quad (66)$$

399 To consider the momentum exchange, the Lagrangian velocity is modified as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{U}_{f,c}^L &= \mathbf{U}_{f,c}^{L-} + \Delta \mathbf{U}_{f,c} \\ \mathbf{U}_{sc}^L &= \mathbf{U}_{sc}^{L-} + \Delta \mathbf{U}_{sc} \end{aligned} \quad (67)$$

400 where the cell-centered intermediate velocity can be calculated by:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{U}_{f,c}^{L-} &= \frac{(m\mathbf{U})_{f,c}^{L-}}{m_{f,c}^L} \\ \mathbf{U}_{sc}^{L-} &= \frac{(m\mathbf{U})_{sc}^{L-}}{m_{sc}^L} \end{aligned} \quad (68)$$

401 And the increment of the velocity $\mathbf{U}_{f,c}$, $\Delta\mathbf{U}_{sc}$ can be computed by solving
 402 the linear equation with $i,j = 1:N$ as:

$$\begin{vmatrix} (1 + \beta_{ij}) & -\beta_{ij} \\ -\beta_{ji} & (1 + \beta_{ji}) \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} \Delta\mathbf{U}_{i,c} \\ \Delta\mathbf{U}_{j,c} \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} \beta_{ij}(\mathbf{U}_{i,c}^{L-} - \mathbf{U}_{j,c}^{L-}) \\ \beta_{ji}(\mathbf{U}_{j,c}^{L-} - \mathbf{U}_{i,c}^{L-}) \end{vmatrix}$$

403 To consider the energy exchange, the Lagrangian temperature is modified as:

$$\begin{aligned} T_{f,c}^L &= T_{f,c}^{L-} + \Delta T_{f,c} \\ T_{sc}^L &= T_{sc}^{L-} + \Delta T_{sc} \end{aligned} \quad (69)$$

404 where the cell-centered intermediate temperature can be calculated by:

$$\begin{aligned} T_{f,c}^{L-} &= \frac{(mT)_{f,c}^{L-}}{m_{f,c}^L c_v} \\ T_{sc}^{L-} &= \frac{(mT)_{sc}^{L-}}{m_{sc}^L c_v} \end{aligned} \quad (70)$$

405 And the increment of the velocity can be computed by solving the linear
 406 equation with $i,j = 1:N$ as:

$$\begin{vmatrix} (1 + \eta_{ij}) & -\eta_{ij} \\ -\eta_{ji} & (1 + \eta_{ji}) \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} \Delta T_{i,c} \\ \Delta T_{j,c} \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} \eta_{ij}(T_{i,c}^{L-} - T_{j,c}^{L-}) \\ \eta_{ji}(T_{j,c}^{L-} - T_{i,c}^{L-}) \end{vmatrix}$$

407 Finally, we obtain the cell-centered solid acceleration and temperature rate
 408 as:

$$d\mathbf{U}_{sc}^L = \frac{(m\mathbf{U})_{sc}^L - (m\mathbf{U})_{sc}^n}{m_{sc}^L \Delta t} \quad (71)$$

409

$$dT_{sc}^L = \frac{(me)_{sc}^L - (me)_{sc}^n}{m_{sc}^L c_v \Delta t} \quad (72)$$

410 *Compute Lagrangian specific volume of the fluid phase*

411 To compute the Lagrangian value of the specific volume of the fluid phase,
 412 we need to compute the Lagrangian temperature rate as below:

$$T_{f,c}^{n+1} = \frac{(me)_{f,c}^L}{m_{f,c}^L c_v} \quad (73)$$

413

$$\frac{D_f T_{f,c}}{Dt} = \frac{T_{f,c}^{n+1} - T_{f,c}^n}{\Delta t} \quad (74)$$

414 As such, the Lagrangian specific volume rate is:

$$\Delta(mv)_{f,c} = Vf_{f,c}^\phi \nabla \cdot \mathbf{U} + (\phi_{f,c} \alpha_{f,c} \frac{D_f T_{f,c}}{Dt} - f_{f,c}^\phi \sum_{n=1}^N \phi_{nc} \alpha_{nc} \frac{D_n T_{n,c}}{Dt}) \quad (75)$$

415 where $f_f^\phi = (\phi_f \kappa_f) / (\sum_{n=1}^N \phi_n \kappa_n)$ and $\mathbf{U} = \nabla \cdot (\sum_{s=1}^{N_s} \phi_{sc} \mathbf{U}_{sc} + \sum_{f=1}^{N_f} \phi_{fc} \mathbf{U}_{f,c})$.
 416 Finally, the Lagrangian specific volume is:

$$(mv)_{f,c}^L = V \bar{\rho}_{f,c}^n v_{f,c}^n + \Delta(mv)_{f,c} \quad (76)$$

417 *Compute advection term and advance in time*

418 The time advanced mass, linear momentum, energy and specific volume
 419 are:

$$m_{f,c}^{n+1} = m_{f,c}^L - \Delta t \nabla \cdot (\bar{\rho}_{f,c}^L \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^L) \quad (77)$$

$$(m\mathbf{U})_{f,c}^{n+1} = (m\mathbf{U})_{f,c}^L - \Delta t \nabla \cdot ((\bar{\rho}\mathbf{U})_{f,c}^L \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^L) \quad (78)$$

$$(me)_{f,c}^{n+1} = (me)_{f,c}^L - \Delta t \nabla \cdot ((\bar{\rho}c_v T)_{f,c}^L \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^L) \quad (79)$$

$$(mv)_{f,c}^{n+1} = (mv)_{f,c}^L - \Delta t \nabla \cdot ((\bar{\rho}v)_{f,c}^L \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^L) \quad (80)$$

423 Finally, the state variables of the fluid phases of the next time step are:

$$\bar{\rho}_{f,c}^{n+1} = \frac{m_{f,c}^{n+1}}{V} \quad (81)$$

$$\mathbf{U}_{f,c}^{n+1} = \frac{(m\mathbf{U})_{f,c}^{n+1}}{m_{f,c}^{n+1}} \quad (82)$$

$$T_{f,c}^{n+1} = \frac{(me)_{f,c}^{n+1}}{m_{f,c}^{n+1}} \quad (83)$$

$$v_{f,c}^{n+1} = \frac{(mv)_{f,c}^{n+1}}{m_{f,c}^{n+1}} \quad (84)$$

427 *Interpolate from cell to node of the solid phase*

428 First we interpolate the acceleration, velocity and temperature rate to
429 the node as below:

$$\mathbf{a}_{si}^n = \sum S_{ci} d\mathbf{U}_{sc}^L \quad (85)$$

430

$$\mathbf{U}_{si}^{n+1} = \sum S_{ci} d\mathbf{U}_{sc}^L \Delta t \quad (86)$$

431

$$dT_{si}^n = \sum S_{ci} dT_{sc}^L \quad (87)$$

432 Then the boundary condition and contact forces f_{si}^{fric} are applied to the nodal
433 velocity and the acceleration is modified by:

$$\mathbf{a}_{si}^n = \frac{\mathbf{v}_{si}^{n+1} - \mathbf{v}_{si}^n}{\Delta t} \quad (88)$$

434 *Update the particle variables*

435 The state variables of the solid phase $[\mathbf{U}_{sp}^{n+1}, \mathbf{x}_{sp}^{n+1}, \nabla \mathbf{U}_{sp}^{n+1}, T_{sp}^{n+1}, \nabla T_{sp}^{n+1}, \mathbf{F}_{sp}^{n+1}, V_{sp}^{n+1}]$
436 (velocity, position, velocity gradient, temperature, temperature gradient, de-
437 formation gradient, volume) are updated as:

$$\mathbf{U}_{sp}^{n+1} = \mathbf{U}_{sp}^n + \sum S_{sp} \mathbf{a}_{si}^n \Delta t \quad (89)$$

438

$$\mathbf{x}_{sp}^{n+1} = \mathbf{x}_{sp}^n + \sum S_{sp} \mathbf{U}_{si}^{n+1} \Delta t \quad (90)$$

439

$$\nabla \mathbf{U}_{sp}^{n+1} = \sum \nabla S_{sp} \mathbf{U}_{si}^{n+1} \quad (91)$$

440

$$T_{sp}^{n+1} = T_{sp}^n + \sum S_{sp} dT_{si}^n \Delta t \quad (92)$$

441

$$\nabla T_{sp}^{n+1} = \sum \nabla S_{sp} T_{si}^n \Delta t \quad (93)$$

442

$$\mathbf{F}_{sp}^{n+1} = (\mathbf{I} + \nabla \mathbf{U}_{sp}^{n+1} \Delta t) \mathbf{F}_{sp}^n \quad (94)$$

443

$$V_{sp}^{n+1} = \det(\mathbf{F}_{sp}^{n+1}) V_{sp}^o \quad (95)$$

444 Finally, the effective stress $(\boldsymbol{\sigma}')^{n+1}$ is updated from the constitutive model
445 and the pore water pressure is interpolated from the cell as:

$$p_f^{n+1} = \sum S_{si} P_c^{n+1} \quad (96)$$

446 **Numerical examples**

447 All input files and the analytical calculations in this section are provided
 448 in the Github repository (https://github.com/QuocAnh90/Uintah_NTNU)
 449 for the reproduction of the numerical results.

450 To prevent repetition, we present the parameters of water and air, which
 451 remain consistent across all simulations. The water has a bulk modulus of 2
 452 GPa, a density of 998 kg/m³ at a reference temperature of 5 degrees Celsius
 453 and a reference pressure of 10325 Pa (1atm), a dynamic viscosity μ_f of 1
 454 mPa s). The air has a ideal gas with a density of 1.17 kg/m³ at a reference
 455 temperature of 5 degrees Celsius and a reference pressure of 10325 Pa (1atm),
 456 a dynamic viscosity μ_f of $18.45E^{-3}$ mPa s).

457 *Fluid Flow through isothermal porous media*

Figure 7: Numerical results of the fluid flow through isothermal porous media

458 Fluid flow through porous media is important in many engineering disci-
 459 plines, like predicting water flow in soil. Fluid flow velocity in one dimension
 460 can be calculated from the porous media's hydraulic conductivity K as:

461

$$U_f = K \frac{\Delta p_f}{L} \quad (97)$$

462 If the Carman-Kozeny formula is adopted $F = 10\phi_s/(1 - \phi_s)^2$, the hydraulic
 463 conductivity will be expressed as $K = D_p^2(1 - \phi_s)^3\rho_f g/180\phi_s^2\mu_f$. Then, the
 464 analytical formula of average velocity in one dimension through the porous
 465 media is:

466

$$U_f = \frac{1}{n} \frac{D_p^2(1 - \phi_s)^3}{180\phi_s^2\mu_f} \frac{\Delta p_f}{L} \quad (98)$$

467 Our numerical model is validated by modeling fluid flow through a 1m
 468 long porous media. The porous media is modeled by elastic material with
 469 Young's modulus is 10 MPa, Poisson's ratio is 0.3, and density is 2650 kg/m³.
 470 The volume fraction of porous media ϕ_s is [0.6, 0.62, 0.66, 0.68, 0.7] and the
 471 average grain diameter d is 1mm. The model is discretized in 20 finite element
 472 and the porous media in 10 finite element with 1 material point per element.
 473 The pressure gradient is applied with three different value [0.25, 0.5, 1] atm.
 474 Figure 7 shows a good agreement of fluid flow prediction between the theory
 475 and the model.

476 *Isothermal consolidation*

Figure 8: Comparison between analytical solution and numerical solution

477 A common benchmark for a fully saturated porous media is the simulation
 478 of one-dimensional consolidation. Using the Carman-Kozeny formula, the

Figure 9: Model schematic [23]

479 time-dependent pressure can be calculated as:

$$p_f = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{2F_{ext}}{M} \sin\left(\frac{Mz}{H}\right) e^{-M^2 T_v} \quad \text{with } M = \frac{\pi}{2}(2m + 1) \quad (99)$$

480 where the consolidation rate $T_v = C_v t / H^2$, the consolidation coefficient $C_v =$
 481 $E_v n^3 d^2 / (180(1 - n)^2 \mu)$ and the Oedometer modulus $E_v = E(1 - \nu) / (1 +$
 482 $\nu) / (1 - 2\nu)$. Our numerical model is validated by modeling the consolidation
 483 of a 1m column. The porous media is modeled by elastic material with
 484 Young's modulus is 10 MPa, Poisson's ratio is 0.3, and density is 2650 kg/m³.
 485 The volume fraction of porous media ϕ_s is 0.7 which is equivalent to the
 486 porosity of 0.3 and the average grain diameter d is 1mm. The model is
 487 discretized in 100 finite element with 1 material point per element. The
 488 external pressure applies to the top of the column is 10 kPa. Figure 8 shows
 489 a good agreement of fluid flow prediction between the theory and the model.

490 *Thermal induced cavity flow*

491 Another benchmark is the thermal induced cavity flow in porous me-
 492 dia. Temperature and velocity distributions are calculated for a square non-
 493 deformable saturated porous media The top and bottom walls are insulated,
 494 and the left and right walls are at fixed temperature gradient of 1 degree. The
 495 fluid motion at steady state are cavity flow due to the temperature induced

Figure 10: Comparison between MPMICE model and FEM model

496 density variation. The numerical is validated by comparing with the numer-
 497 ical solution of the finite element method. The porous media is modeled
 498 by non deformable material, and density is 2500 kg/m³. The specific heat
 499 capacity of the water and porous skeleton are 4181 J/kg.K and 835 J/kg.K
 500 respectively. The thermal conductivity of the water and porous skeleton are
 501 0.598 W/m.K and 0.4 W/m.K. The volume fraction of porous media ϕ_s is 0.6
 502 which is equivalent to the porosity of 0.4 and the average grain diameter d is
 503 1mm. The model is discretized in 20 x 20 finite element with 4 material point
 504 per element. Figure 10 shows a good agreement of numerical results of the
 505 model compared with the numerical solution of the finite element method.

506 *Underwater debris flow*

507 The numerical example is validated using the experimental work of Rza-
 508 dkiewicz et al. on submarine debris flow [24]. In their experiment, sand within
 509 a triangular box is released and slides along a rigid bed inclined at 45 degrees
 510 under water (see Figure 11). The material properties in the numerical model
 511 are selected based on the experiment by Rzadkiewicz et al. [24]. The sand
 512 is characterized by a saturated density of 1985 kg/m³ and a friction angle
 513 of 10 degrees. The effect of Young's modulus on debris flow run-out is neg-
 514 ligible due to the extreme deformation of the debris, so a Young's modulus

Figure 11: Model schematic

515 of 50 MPa with a Poisson's ratio of 0.25 is chosen. The rigid bed, being
 516 much stiffer, has bulk modulus and shear modulus values of $117E^7$ Pa and
 517 $43.8E^7$ Pa, respectively. The numerical parameters used in this example are
 518 presented in Table 1.

519 The boundary conditions imposed in the numerical model are as follows: on
 520 all boundary faces, the velocity is set to zero ($U = 0$ m/s) and the tempera-
 521 ture is set to 5 degrees Celsius ($T = 5^\circ\text{C}$). At the top boundary, the pressure
 522 has a Neumann boundary condition of $dp/dx = 0$ kPa, and the density has
 523 a Neumann boundary condition of $d\rho/dx = 0$ kg/m^3 . The background mesh
 524 consists of 700 x 400 cells, resulting in a total of 280,000 cells. Each cell in
 525 the debris flow and rigid bed contains 2 x 2 material points.

526 Figure 13b illustrates snapshots of the underwater debris flow sliding, demon-
 527 strating that the model captures the typical hydroplaning mechanism of the
 528 debris flow. Hydroplaning refers to the lifting of the debris flow, causing it
 529 to lose contact with the bottom layer. The elevation of the free surface at
 530 0.4s and 0.8s is compared between our proposed method and other methods
 531 in Figure 12. Our computed results align well with the experimental results
 532 [7].

533 Unlike other computational models that rely on total stress analysis [5, 6, 7,
 534 8], our proposed model utilizes effective stress analysis, enabling the analy-
 535 sis of water pressure and temperature within the debris flow. Additionally,
 536 we investigate the differences between underwater debris flow and saturated
 537 debris flow in terms of their interaction with obstacles. Figure 13 presents

538 snapshots of simulations of both underwater and saturated debris flow. The
 539 saturated debris flow (Figure 13a) exhibits behavior similar to frictional flow,
 540 where grains have contact forces with each other. Conversely, the underwa-
 541 ter debris flow (Figure 13b) behaves like turbulent flow, with grains being
 542 separated from each other and exhibiting no contact forces (as reflected by
 the near-zero effective stress in the turbulence domain).

Materials	Bulk modul (Pa)	Shear modul (Pa)	Density (kg/m ³)	Temp (C)	Dynamic viscosity (Pa s)	Friction angle (degrees)
Water (at surface)	2.15e9	-	999.8	5	855e-6	-
Air (at top boundary)	-	-	1.177	5	18.45e-6	-
Sand (porous media)	8.33e6	20e6	1985	5	-	10
Rigid bed (solid)	117e7	43.8e7	8900	5	-	-

Table 1: Numerical parameters for the underwater submarine debris

543

Figure 12: Evolution of water level in the simulation of underwater debris flow

(a) saturated debris flow using MPM (b) underwater debris flow using MPMICE

Figure 13: Simulation of Debris Flow: Mean Effective Stress Distribution (Green Color Indicates Near-Zero Effective Stress)

Figure 14: Seismic loading

Figure 15: Material points prescribed velocity as kinematic boundary condition [25]

545 An experimental study conducted by Hiraoka et al. [26] aimed to inves-
546 tigate the influence of seismic shaking on the deformation of a 0.5 m-high
547 sand slope. The sand used in the experiment was partially saturated, with a
548 moisture content of 10 percent. The provided soil parameters for the Mohr
549 Coulomb model include the effective friction angle of 23 degrees, apparent
550 cohesion of 0.78 kPa, Young's modulus of 2.57 MPa, and Poisson's ratio of
551 0.33, and moist unit weight of 16.5 kN/m³. The soil's dilatancy angle was
552 assumed to be 0 [26]. The experimental setup consisted of a shaking table
553 box with a steel horizontal base and smooth glass vertical sidewalls. Laser

554 sensors were used to monitor the displacement of the slope's toe and crest.
555 Figure 14 displays the velocity-time history employed in the experiment.

Figure 16: Numerical model of the seismic-induced slope failure with displacement color

556 To simulate the seismic loading in our numerical model, we adopted a
557 method presented by Alsardi et al. [25], which involves specifying the velocity
558 at the corresponding material points representing either the shaking table or
559 the bedrock at the site (see Figure 15). In our simulation, we considered the
560 horizontal base to be fully rough and the vertical contact to be fully smooth.
561 The initial stress condition was initiated using gravity and seismic loading
562 induced the slope failure (see Figure 16).
563 Previous studies by Bhandari et al. [27], Alsardi et al. [25], and Hiraoka et
564 al. [26] attempted to model this experiment using MPM and SPH models. In
565 this study, we compared our results with those obtained from other particle-
566 based methods (Figure 17). The main difference is that we did not apply
567 5 percent numerical damping in our model, unlike the other methods. We
568 found that the final displacement of the slope toe in our MPM model was
569 higher than that observed in the experiment. Nevertheless, the validation of
570 the Mohr-Coulomb model under seismic response demonstrated a reasonable
571 soil behavior in terms of displacement.

Figure 17: Displacement of the toe of the slope

572 Earthquake-induced submarine landslides

Figure 18: Numerical simulation of the earthquake-induced submarine landslide

Figure 19: Ground acceleration profile, frequency of 2Hz and magnitude of 1g

573 In the final example, we perform numerical analysis of the earthquake
 574 induced submarine landslides. A plane strain model with the slope under
 575 water is shown in Figure 18. A 20m high slope with slope gradient of 45
 576 degrees is placed in a horizontal and vertical structure which was used to
 577 be a skaing table to apply earthquake loading. We simplify the earthquake
 578 loading by simulating the ground shaking for 20 seconds with the constant
 579 ground acceleration of 1g and a constant frequency of 2Hz (Figure 19a). The
 580 ground motion is applied in terms of velocity (Figure 19b). An earthquake
 581 of this magnitude is possible. For instance, in the case of the 2023 Turkey-
 582 Syria Earthquake, significant ground shaking with peak ground acceleration
 583 exceeding 1g was observed at numerous locations. This serves as an example
 584 of the practical occurrence of such high levels of ground acceleration during
 585 seismic events. To generate the seismic loading, the same method was used
 586 as presented in the previous numerical example.

Figure 20: Mobilized friction angle in Mohr Coulomb model

587 A non-associated Mohr-Coulomb model is used for the soil. The soil grain
588 has the density of 2650 kg/m^3 , Young's modulus of 10 kPa and Poisson's
589 ratio of 0.3 and zero cohesion. The mobilized friction angle ϕ'_m is governed
590 following the softening curve (see Figure 20) with the peak friction angle ϕ'_p
591 of 45 degrees and the residual friction angle ϕ'_r of 10 degrees. The porosity
592 is 0.3 and the average grain size of the soil is around $0.1 \mu\text{m}$ to mimic the
593 undrained behavior. The mobilized dilatancy angle is calculated from the
594 Rowe's stress dilatancy theory [28] as follow:

$$\sin \psi'_m = \frac{\sin \phi'_m - \sin \phi'_r}{1 - (\sin \phi'_r \sin \phi'_m)} \quad (100)$$

595 The solid plane is modeled as a rigid body acted as a shaking table. The
596 contact between horizontal plane and the sand is the frictional contact with
597 the friction coefficient of 0.1. No artificial damping is applied in the simu-
598 lation. The contact between vertical plane and the sand is considered to be
599 smooth with zero friction coefficient. On all boundary faces, the symmet-
600 ric boundary condition is imposed, while the Neumann boundary condition
601 is imposed at the top boundary for pressure ($dp/dx = 0 \text{ kPa}$) and density
602 ($d\rho/dx = 0 \text{ kg/m}^3$). Symmetric boundary condition refers to a condition
603 where the normal component of the velocity at the boundary face is set to
604 zero, and the tangential component is equal to the tangential component of
605 the neighboring cells. The mesh size is $0.25 \times 0.25\text{m}$ with 300852 element
606 cells and 142316 material points. The simulation takes a couple of hours to
607 perform 60 seconds of the simulation using 4096 CPUs.

Figure 21: Shear strain during the earthquake-induced submarine landslides

608 We demonstrate the entire process and the mechanism of the earthquake-
 609 induced submarine landslides by showing the shear strain (Figure 21), the
 610 pore water pressure in atm (Figure 22) and the velocity (Figure 23). The
 611 failure mechanism can be characterized as the progressive failure mechanism.
 612 Here are some numerical observation:

- 613 1. At the initial of the seismic event, the seismic loading triggers the
 614 first slide at 3 seconds. At 4 seconds, the debris start to move with the
 615 maximum speed of around 2-3 m/s with multiple shear band developed
 616 in the slope. The wave generated from the submarine slide is around
 617 2-3m towards the slide direction.

Figure 22: pore water pressure during the earthquake-induced submarine landslides

- 618 2. When the onset of the shear band occurs in the slope (for example
 619 at 4 seconds and 20 seconds), the negative excess pore water pressure
 620 is developed along this shear band with pore water pressure is under
 621 1atm. This is a typical dilatancy behavior when the soil is sheared
 622 rapidly in the undrained behavior.
- 623 3. When the seismic loading ends at 23 seconds, the last shear band is
 624 mobilized and the slope soon reaches to the final deposition. No more
 625 progressive failure developed in the slope. The turbulent flow developed
 626 as the interaction between debris flow and seawater.

627 Overall, we show the completed process of the earthquake-induced submarine
 628 landslides involving (1) earthquake triggering mechanism, (2) the onset of the
 629 shear band with the development of negative excess pore water pressure, (3)
 630 progressive failure mechanism, (4) submarine landslide induced wave to final
 631 deposition.

Figure 23: Velocity during the earthquake-induced submarine landslides

632 Conclusions

633 We have presented a numerical approach MPMICE for the simulation
 634 of large deformation soil-fluid-structure interaction, emphasizing the simu-
 635 lation of the earthquake-induced submarine landslides. The model uses (1)
 636 the Material Point Method for capturing the large deformation of iso-thermal
 637 porous media and solid structures and (2) Implicit Continuous Eulerian (com-
 638 pressible, conservative multi-material CFD formulation) for modeling the
 639 complex fluid flow including turbulence. This model is implemented in the
 640 high-performance Uintah computational framework and validated against an-
 641 alytical solution and experiment. We then demonstrate the capability of the
 642 model to simulate the entire process of the earthquake induced submarine
 643 landslides.

644 **Acknowledgements**

645 The authors gratefully acknowledge Dr. James Guilkey and Dr. Todd
 646 Harman from the University of Utah for sharing the insight on the theoretical
 647 framework of MPMICE which this work is based. This project has received
 648 funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation
 649 program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) Individual Fel-
 650 lowship (Project SUBSLIDE “Submarine landslides and their impacts on
 651 offshore infrastructures”) grant agreement 101022007. The authors would
 652 also like to acknowledge the support from the Research Council of Norway
 653 through its Centers of Excellence funding scheme, project number 262644
 654 Porelab. The computations were performed on High Performance Comput-
 655 ing resources provided by UNINETT Sigma2 - the National Infrastructure
 656 for High Performance Computing and Data Storage in Norway.

657 **Appendix: Equation derivation**

658 Before deriving the governing equation, we define the Lagrangian deriva-
 659 tive for a state variable f as:

$$\frac{D_f f}{Dt} = \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + \mathbf{U}_f \cdot \nabla f \quad \frac{D_s f}{Dt} = \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + \mathbf{U}_s \cdot \nabla f \quad (101)$$

we use some definition following [16] as below:

$$-\frac{1}{V} \left[\frac{\partial V_f}{\partial p} \right] \equiv \kappa_f \quad \text{isothermal compressibility of fluid} \quad (102)$$

$$\frac{1}{V} \left[\frac{\partial V_f}{\partial T} \right] \equiv \alpha_f \quad \text{contant pressure thermal expansivity of fluid} \quad (103)$$

660 Then, the rate of volume with incompressible solid grains are calculated as
 661 belows:

$$\frac{1}{V} \frac{D_f V_f}{Dt} = \frac{1}{V} \left(\left[\frac{\partial V_f}{\partial p} \right] \frac{D_f P_{eq}}{Dt} + \left[\frac{\partial V_f}{\partial T} \right] \frac{D_f T}{Dt} \right) = \frac{1}{V} \left(-\kappa_f \frac{D_f P_{eq}}{Dt} + \alpha_f \frac{D_f T}{Dt} \right) \quad (104)$$

662 **Evolution of porosity**

663 Solving the solid mass balance equation (4) with the definition of solid
 664 mass in equation (2), it leads to the rate of porosity as belows:

$$\frac{D_s m_s}{Dt} = \frac{D_s(\phi_s \rho_s V)}{Dt} = \rho_s V \frac{D_s \phi_s}{Dt} + \phi_s V \frac{D_s \rho_s}{Dt} + \phi_s \rho_s \frac{D_s V}{Dt} = 0 \quad (105)$$

665 The soil grains are assumed to be incompressible, therefore, term 2 in the
 666 right hand side is zero. leading to:

$$V \frac{D_s \phi_s}{Dt} + \phi_s \frac{D_s V}{Dt} = 0 \quad (106)$$

667 Dividing all terms with V with the equation $\frac{1}{V} \frac{D_s V}{Dt} = \nabla \cdot \mathbf{U}_s$, it leads to:

$$\frac{D_s n}{Dt} = \frac{\partial n}{\partial t} + \mathbf{U}_s \cdot \nabla n = \phi_s \nabla \cdot \mathbf{U}_s \quad (107)$$

668 *Momentum conservation*

669 The linear momentum balance equations for the fluid phases based on
 670 mixture theory are:

$$671 \quad \frac{1}{V} \frac{D_f(m_f \mathbf{U}_f)}{Dt} = \nabla \cdot (-\phi_f p_f \mathbf{I}) + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_f + \bar{\rho}_f \mathbf{b} + \sum \mathbf{f}_d + \mathbf{f}_b \quad (108)$$

672 On the right hand sand, the first term is the divergence of partial fluid phase
 673 stress, the third term is the body force, the fourth term is the drag force
 674 (momentum exchange) and the fifth term is the buoyant force described in
 675 [29] for the immiscible mixtures. The buoyant force is in the form as belows:

$$\mathbf{f}_b = \boldsymbol{\sigma}_f \nabla(n) \quad (109)$$

676 As a result, the linear momentum balance equations for the fluid phases
 677 become as:

$$\frac{1}{V} \frac{D_f(m_f \mathbf{U}_f)}{Dt} = \frac{1}{V} \left[\frac{\partial(m_f \mathbf{U}_f)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (m_f \mathbf{U}_f \mathbf{U}_f) \right] = -\phi_f \nabla p_f + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_f + \bar{\rho}_f \mathbf{b} + \sum \mathbf{f}_d \quad (110)$$

678 The Reynolds stress component can be included in the term $\boldsymbol{\tau}_f$ to consider the
 679 turbulent effects if needed. To derive the linear momentum balance equation
 680 for the solid phase, we begin with the linear momentum balance equation for
 681 the mixture as:

$$\frac{1}{V} \frac{D_f(m_f \mathbf{U}_f)}{Dt} + \frac{1}{V} \frac{D_s(m_s \mathbf{U}_s)}{Dt} = \nabla \cdot (\boldsymbol{\sigma}) + \bar{\rho}_f \mathbf{b} + \bar{\rho}_s \mathbf{b} \quad (111)$$

682 Combining Terzaghi's equation (3) and subtracting both sides with equation
 683 (110), we obtain the linear momentum balance equations for the solid phase
 684 as:

$$\frac{1}{V} \frac{D_s(m_s \mathbf{U}_s)}{Dt} = \nabla \cdot (\boldsymbol{\sigma}') - \phi_s \nabla p_f + \bar{\rho}_s \mathbf{b} - \sum \mathbf{f}_d + \sum \mathbf{f}_{fric} \quad (112)$$

685 Here the \mathbf{f}_{fric} stems from the soil-structure interaction following the contact
 686 law between the soil/structure interfaces.

687 *Energy conservation*

688 We adopt the general form of the total energy balance equation for the
 689 porous media from [30], the total energy balance equations for the fluid phases
 690 are:

$$\frac{1}{V} \frac{D_f(m_f(e_f + 0.5\mathbf{U}_f^2))}{Dt} = \nabla \cdot (-n p_f \mathbf{I}) \cdot \mathbf{U}_f + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q}_f + (\bar{\rho}_f \mathbf{b}) \cdot \mathbf{U}_f + \sum \mathbf{f}_d \cdot \mathbf{U}_f + \sum q_{sf} \quad (113)$$

691 Applying the product rule $D(m\mathbf{U}^2) = D(m\mathbf{U} \cdot \mathbf{U}) = 2\mathbf{U} \cdot D(m\mathbf{U})$, the left
 692 hand side of equation (113) becomes:

$$\frac{1}{V} \frac{D_f(m_f(e_f + 0.5\mathbf{U}_f^2))}{Dt} = \frac{1}{V} \frac{D_f(m_f e_f)}{Dt} + \frac{1}{V} \frac{D_f(m_f \mathbf{U}_f)}{Dt} \cdot \mathbf{U}_f \quad (114)$$

694 Combining equations (110), (113), (114), we obtain the final form of the
 695 internal energy balance equation for the fluid phases as:

$$\frac{1}{V} \frac{D_f(m_f e_f)}{Dt} = \frac{1}{V} \left[\frac{\partial(m_f e_f)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (m_f e_f \mathbf{U}_f) \right] = \bar{\rho}_f p_f \frac{D_f v_f}{Dt} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q}_f + \sum q_{sf} \quad (115)$$

696 On the right hand side, the terms include the average pressure-volume work,
 697 the average viscous dissipation, the thermal transport and the energy ex-
 698 change between solid and fluid respectively. The heat flux is $\mathbf{q}_f = \bar{\rho}_f \beta_f \nabla T_f$
 699 with β_f being the thermal conductivity coefficient. To derive the internal
 700 energy balance equation for the solid phase, we introduce the rate of the
 701 internal energy for the thermoelastic materials as a function of elastic strain
 702 tensor $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^e$ and temperature T_s as belows:

$$\frac{m_s}{V} \frac{D_s(e_s)}{Dt} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}' : \frac{D_s(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^e)}{Dt} + \frac{D_s(e_s)}{D_s(T_s)} \frac{D_s(T_s)}{Dt} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}' : \frac{D_s(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^e)}{Dt} + c_v \frac{D_s(T_s)}{Dt} \quad (116)$$

703 c_v is the specific heat at the constant volume of the solid materials. The total
 704 energy balance equation for the mixture based on [30] can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{V} \frac{D_f(m_f(e_f + 0.5\mathbf{U}_f^2))}{Dt} + \frac{1}{V} \frac{D_s(m_s(e_s + 0.5\mathbf{U}_s^2))}{Dt} &= \nabla \cdot (-\phi_f p_f \mathbf{I}) \cdot \mathbf{U}_f \\ &+ \nabla \cdot (\boldsymbol{\sigma}' - \phi_s p_f \mathbf{I}) \cdot \mathbf{U}_s + (-\phi_f p_f \mathbf{I}) : \nabla \mathbf{U}_f + \boldsymbol{\sigma}' : \nabla \mathbf{U}_s \\ &+ (\bar{\rho}_f \mathbf{b}) \cdot \mathbf{U}_f + (\bar{\rho}_s \mathbf{b}) \cdot \mathbf{U}_s + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q}_f + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q}_s + \sum \mathbf{f}_d \cdot (\mathbf{U}_f - \mathbf{U}_s) \end{aligned} \quad (117)$$

706 Subtracting equation (117), (116) to equations (113) and (112), we obtained
 707 the internal energy balance equation for solid phase as:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}' : \frac{D_s(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^e)}{Dt} + \frac{m_s}{V} c_v \frac{D_s(T_s)}{Dt} = \Delta W_s + \Delta W_{friction} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q}_s - \sum q_{sf} \quad (118)$$

708 On the right hand side, the terms include the work rate from frictional sliding
 709 between solid materials $\Delta W_{friction}$, thermal transport and energy exchange
 710 between solid and fluid respectively. The heat flux is $\mathbf{q}_s = \bar{\rho}_s \beta_s \nabla T_s$ with β_s
 711 being the thermal conductivity of the solid materials, the mechanical work
 712 rate $\Delta W_s = \boldsymbol{\sigma}' : \frac{D_s(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s)}{Dt} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}' : \left(\frac{D_s(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^e)}{Dt} + \frac{D_s(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^p)}{Dt} \right)$ computed from the constitutive
 713 model with $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^p$ is the plastic strain tensor, . By subtracting the term $\boldsymbol{\sigma}' : \frac{D_s(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^e)}{Dt}$,
 714 we get the final form of the energy balance equation as:

$$\frac{m_s}{V} c_v \frac{D_s(T_s)}{Dt} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}' : \frac{D_s(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_s^p)}{Dt} + \Delta W_{friction} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q}_s - \sum q_{sf} \quad (119)$$

715 *Advanced Fluid Pressure*

716 The discretization of the pressure equation begins with the Lagrangian
 717 cell face velocity and the equation for the pressure as:

$$\bar{\rho}_{f,FC} \frac{\mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^{n+1} - \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^n}{dt} = n \nabla^{FC} P_{f,c}^{n+1} + \bar{\rho}_{f,FC} \mathbf{b} \quad (120)$$

718

$$\kappa \frac{dP}{dt} = \nabla^c \cdot \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^{n+1} \quad (121)$$

719 The divergence of the equation (120) with $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{b} = 0$ is:

$$\nabla^c \cdot \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^{n+1} - \nabla^c \cdot \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^n = \nabla^c \frac{\Delta t}{\rho_{f,FC}^n} \cdot \nabla^{FC} (P_{f,c}^n + \Delta P_{f,c}^n) \quad (122)$$

720 To solve this equation, we define the cell face intermediate velocity $\mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^*$ as:

$$\bar{\rho}_{f,FC} \frac{\mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^* - \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^n}{\Delta t} = n \nabla^{FC} P_{f,c}^n + \bar{\rho}_{f,FC} \mathbf{b} \quad (123)$$

721 The divergence of the equation (123) is:

$$\nabla^c \cdot \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^* - \nabla^c \cdot \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^n = \nabla^c \frac{\Delta t}{\rho_{f,FC}^n} \cdot \nabla^{FC} P_{f,c}^n \quad (124)$$

722 Combining equations (121, 122, 124), it leads to:

$$\left(\kappa - \nabla^c \frac{\Delta t}{\rho_{f,FC}^n} \cdot \nabla^{FC} \right) \Delta P_{fc}^n = -\nabla^c \cdot \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^* \quad (125)$$

723 When the fluid is incompressible, κ approaches to zero and the equation
724 (125) becomes the Poisson's equation for the incompressible fluid flow.

725 *Momentum and Energy exchange with an implicit solver*

726 Considering the fluid momentum balance equation as:

$$(m\mathbf{U})_{f,FC}^{n+1} = (m\mathbf{U})_{f,FC}^n - \Delta t(Vn\nabla^{FC} P_{f,c}^n + m_f \mathbf{b}) + VK\Delta t(\mathbf{U}_{s,FC}^{n+1} - \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^{n+1}) \quad (126)$$

727 And assuming $m_{f,FC}^{n+1} = m_{f,FC}^n$, we get:

$$\mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^{n+1} = \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^n - \Delta t\left(\frac{\nabla^{FC} P_{fc}^n}{\rho_{f,FC}^n} + \mathbf{b}\right) + \frac{\Delta t K}{\bar{\rho}_{f,FC}^n}(\mathbf{U}_{s,FC}^{n+1} - \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^{n+1}) \quad (127)$$

728 As defined in the section 'Advanced Fluid Pressure', the cell face intermediate
729 fluid velocity $\mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^* = \Delta t(\nabla^{FC} P_{fc}^n / \rho_{f,FC}^n + \mathbf{b})$ is computed as:

$$\mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^{n+1} = \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^* + \frac{\Delta t K}{\bar{\rho}_{f,FC}^n}(\mathbf{U}_{s,FC}^{n+1} - \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^{n+1}) \quad (128)$$

730 Considering the solid momentum balance equation as:

$$(m\mathbf{U})_{s,FC}^{n+1} = (m\mathbf{U})_{s,FC}^n - \Delta t(V\nabla^{FC} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}'^n - V(1-n)\nabla^{FC} P_{f,c}^n + m_s \mathbf{b}) - VK\Delta t(\mathbf{U}_{s,FC}^{n+1} - \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^{n+1}) \quad (129)$$

731 We define the cell face intermediate solid velocity as $\mathbf{U}_{s,FC}^* = \Delta t(\nabla^{FC} \cdot$
732 $\boldsymbol{\sigma}'^n / \bar{\rho}_{s,FC} - \nabla^{FC} P_{f,c}^n / \rho_s + \mathbf{b})$ leading to:

$$\mathbf{U}_{s,FC}^{n+1} = \mathbf{U}_{s,FC}^* - \frac{\Delta t K}{\bar{\rho}_{s,FC}^n}(\mathbf{U}_{s,FC}^{n+1} - \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^{n+1}) \quad (130)$$

733 Combining equation (128) and (130) we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^* + \Delta \mathbf{U}_{f,FC} &= \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^* + \frac{\Delta t K}{\bar{\rho}_{f,FC}^n}(\mathbf{U}_{s,FC}^* + \Delta \mathbf{U}_{s,FC} - \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^* - \Delta \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}) \\ \mathbf{U}_{s,FC}^* + \Delta \mathbf{U}_{s,FC} &= \mathbf{U}_{s,FC}^* - \frac{\Delta t K}{\bar{\rho}_{s,FC}^n}(\mathbf{U}_{s,FC}^* + \Delta \mathbf{U}_{s,FC} - \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^* - \Delta \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}) \end{aligned} \quad (131)$$

734 Rearranging the equation (131), it leads to the linear system of equations as
 735 belows:

$$\begin{vmatrix} (1 + \beta_{12,FC}) & -\beta_{12,FC} \\ -\beta_{21,FC} & (1 + \beta_{21,FC}) \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} \Delta \mathbf{U}_{f,FC} \\ \Delta \mathbf{U}_{s,FC} \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} \beta_{12,FC}(\mathbf{U}_{s,FC}^* - \mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^*) \\ \beta_{21,FC}(\mathbf{U}_{f,FC}^* - \mathbf{U}_{s,FC}^*) \end{vmatrix}$$

736 Solving this linear equations with $\beta_{12,FC} = (\Delta t K) / \bar{\rho}_{f,FC}^n$ and $\beta_{21,FC} =$
 737 $(\Delta t K) / \bar{\rho}_{s,FC}^n$ with K is the momentum exchange coefficient. Similar deriva-
 738 tion can be performed to computed the cell-center velocity increment leading
 739 to:

$$\begin{vmatrix} (1 + \beta_{12c}) & -\beta_{12c} \\ -\beta_{21c} & (1 + \beta_{21c}) \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} \Delta \mathbf{U}_{f,c} \\ \Delta \mathbf{U}_{sc} \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} \beta_{12c}(\mathbf{U}_{sc}^* - \mathbf{U}_{f,c}^*) \\ \beta_{21c}(\mathbf{U}_{f,c}^* - \mathbf{U}_{sc}^*) \end{vmatrix}$$

740 with $\beta_{12c} = (\Delta t K) / \bar{\rho}_{f,c}^n$ and $\beta_{21c} = (\Delta t K) / \bar{\rho}_{sc}^n$ and the cell-centered interme-
 741 diate velocity can be calculated by:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{U}_{f,c}^* &= \mathbf{U}_{f,c}^n + \Delta t \left(-\frac{\nabla P_{f,c}^{n+1}}{\rho_{f,c}^n} + \frac{\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_{f,c}^n}{\bar{\rho}_{f,c}^n} + \mathbf{b} \right) \\ \mathbf{U}_{sc}^* &= \mathbf{U}_{sc}^n + \Delta t \left(\frac{\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}'_c{}^n}{\bar{\rho}_{sc}^n} - \frac{\nabla P_{f,c}^{n+1}}{\rho_s} + \mathbf{b} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (132)$$

742 For generalize multi materials $i, j = 1:N$, the linear equations is in the form
 743 as:

$$\begin{vmatrix} (1 + \beta_{ij}) & -\beta_{ij} \\ -\beta_{ji} & (1 + \beta_{ji}) \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} \Delta \mathbf{U}_i \\ \Delta \mathbf{U}_j \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} \beta_{ij}(\mathbf{U}_i^* - \mathbf{U}_j^*) \\ \beta_{ji}(\mathbf{U}_j^* - \mathbf{U}_i^*) \end{vmatrix}$$

744 Similar approach applied for the energy exchange term leading to:

$$\begin{vmatrix} (1 + \eta_{ij}) & -\eta_{ij} \\ -\eta_{ji} & (1 + \eta_{ji}) \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} \Delta T_i \\ \Delta T_j \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} \eta_{ij}(T_i^n - T_j^n) \\ \eta_{ji}(T_j^n - T_i^n) \end{vmatrix}$$

745 with η is the energy exchange coefficient.

746 References

- 747 [1] D. Yuk, S. Yim, P.-F. Liu, Numerical modeling of submarine mass-
 748 movement generated waves using RANS model, Computers and Geo-
 749 sciences 32 (7) (2006) 927–935. doi:10.1016/j.cageo.2005.10.028.
 750 URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cageo.2005.10.028>

- 751 [2] S. Glimsdal, J.-S. L’Heureux, C. B. Harbitz, F. Løvholt, The 29th jan-
752 uary 2014 submarine landslide at statland, norway—landslide dynamics,
753 tsunami generation, and run-up, *Landslides* 13 (6) (2016) 1435–1444.
754 doi:10.1007/s10346-016-0758-7.
755 URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10346-016-0758-7>
- 756 [3] S. Abadie, D. Morichon, S. Grilli, S. Glockner, Numerical sim-
757 ulation of waves generated by landslides using a multiple-fluid
758 navier–stokes model, *Coastal Engineering* 57 (9) (2010) 779–794.
759 doi:10.1016/j.coastaleng.2010.03.003.
760 URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coastaleng.2010.03.003>
- 761 [4] M. Rauter, S. Viroulet, S. S. Gylfadóttir, W. Fellin, F. Løvholt, Granular
762 porous landslide tsunami modelling – the 2014 lake askja flank collapse,
763 *Nature Communications* 13 (1) (Feb. 2022). doi:10.1038/s41467-022-
764 28296-7.
765 URL <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-28296-7>
- 766 [5] Q.-A. Tran, W. Sołowski, Generalized interpolation material point
767 method modelling of large deformation problems including strain-
768 rate effects – application to penetration and progressive fail-
769 ure problems, *Computers and Geotechnics* 106 (2019) 249–265.
770 doi:10.1016/j.compgeo.2018.10.020.
771 URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compgeo.2018.10.020>
- 772 [6] T. Capone, A. Panizzo, J. J. Monaghan, SPH modelling of water
773 waves generated by submarine landslides, *Journal of Hydraulic Research*
774 48 (sup1) (2010) 80–84. doi:10.1080/00221686.2010.9641248.
775 URL <https://doi.org/10.1080/00221686.2010.9641248>
- 776 [7] X. Zhang, E. Oñate, S. A. G. Torres, J. Bleyer, K. Krabbenhoft, A
777 unified lagrangian formulation for solid and fluid dynamics and its pos-
778 sibility for modelling submarine landslides and their consequences, *Com-
779 puter Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* 343 (2019) 314–
780 338. doi:10.1016/j.cma.2018.07.043.
781 URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cma.2018.07.043>
- 782 [8] R. Dey, B. C. Hawlader, R. Phillips, K. Soga, Numerical modelling
783 of submarine landslides with sensitive clay layers, *Géotechnique* 66 (6)

- 784 (2016) 454–468. doi:10.1680/jgeot.15.p.111.
785 URL <https://doi.org/10.1680/jgeot.15.p.111>
- 786 [9] S. Bandara, K. Soga, Coupling of soil deformation and pore fluid flow
787 using material point method, *Computers and Geotechnics* 63 (2015)
788 199–214. doi:10.1016/j.compgeo.2014.09.009.
789 URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compgeo.2014.09.009>
- 790 [10] A. P. Tampubolon, T. Gast, G. Klár, C. Fu, J. Teran, C. Jiang,
791 K. Museth, Multi-species simulation of porous sand and water
792 mixtures, *ACM Transactions on Graphics* 36 (4) (2017) 1–11.
793 doi:10.1145/3072959.3073651.
794 URL <https://doi.org/10.1145/3072959.3073651>
- 795 [11] A. S. Baumgarten, K. Kamrin, A general constitutive model for dense,
796 fine-particle suspensions validated in many geometries, *Proceedings*
797 *of the National Academy of Sciences* 116 (42) (2019) 20828–20836.
798 doi:10.1073/pnas.1908065116.
799 URL <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1908065116>
- 800 [12] Q.-A. Tran, W. Sołowski, Temporal and null-space filter for the ma-
801 terial point method, *International Journal for Numerical Methods in*
802 *Engineering* 120 (3) (2019) 328–360. doi:10.1002/nme.6138.
803 URL <https://doi.org/10.1002/nme.6138>
- 804 [13] X. Zheng, F. Pisanò, P. J. Vardon, M. A. Hicks, An explicit stabilised
805 material point method for coupled hydromechanical problems in two-
806 phase porous media, *Computers and Geotechnics* 135 (2021) 104112.
807 doi:10.1016/j.compgeo.2021.104112.
808 URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compgeo.2021.104112>
- 809 [14] Q. A. Tran, W. Sołowski, M. Berzins, J. Guilkey, A convected particle
810 least square interpolation material point method, *International Jour-*
811 *nal for Numerical Methods in Engineering* 121 (6) (2019) 1068–1100.
812 doi:10.1002/nme.6257.
813 URL <https://doi.org/10.1002/nme.6257>
- 814 [15] J.-S. Chen, M. Hillman, S.-W. Chi, Meshfree methods: Progress made
815 after 20 years, *Journal of Engineering Mechanics* 143 (4) (Apr. 2017).

- 816 doi:10.1061/(asce)em.1943-7889.0001176.
817 URL [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(asce\)em.1943-7889.0001176](https://doi.org/10.1061/(asce)em.1943-7889.0001176)
- 818 [16] B. A. Kashiwa, A multifield model and method for fluid-structure in-
819 teraction dynamics, Tech. Rep. LA-UR-01-1136, Los Alamos National
820 Laboratory (2001).
- 821 [17] J. Guilkey, T. Harman, B. Banerjee, An eulerian-lagrangian
822 approach for simulating explosions of energetic devices,
823 Computers and Structures 85 (11) (2007) 660 – 674.
824 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruc.2007.01.031>.
825 URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0045794907000429>
- 826 [18] A. S. Baumgarten, B. L. Couchman, K. Kamrin, A coupled finite volume
827 and material point method for two-phase simulation of liquid-sediment
828 and gas-sediment flows, Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and
829 Engineering 384 (2021) 113940. doi:10.1016/j.cma.2021.113940.
830 URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cma.2021.113940>
- 831 [19] S. Bardenhagen, J. Guilkey, K. Roessig, J. Brackbill, W. Witzel,
832 J.C.Foster, An improved contact algorithm for the material point
833 method and application to stress propagation in granular material,
834 CMES-Computer Modeling in Engineering and Sciences 2 (2001) 509–
835 522. doi:10.3970/cmcs.2001.002.509.
- 836 [20] J. A. M. K. R. Beetstra, M. A. van der Hoef, Drag force of intermedi-
837 ate reynolds number flow past mono- and bidisperse arrays of spheres,
838 Fluid Mechanics and Transport Phenomena 53 (2) (2007) 489 – 501.
839 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/aic.11065>.
- 840 [21] R. W. Stewart, The air-sea momentum exchange, Boundary-Layer Me-
841 teorology 6 (1-2) (1974) 151–167. doi:10.1007/bf00232481.
842 URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf00232481>
- 843 [22] S. G. Bardenhagen, E. M. Kober, The generalized interpolation material
844 point method, Computer Modeling in Engineering and Sciences 5 (2004)
845 477–496. doi:10.1016/j.compgeo.2021.104199.
846 URL <https://doi.org/10.3970/cmcs.2004.005.477>
- 847 [23] S. G. Amiri, E. Taheri, A. Lavasan, A hybrid finite element model for
848 non-isothermal two-phase flow in deformable porous media, Computers

- 849 and Geotechnics 135 (2021) 104199. doi:10.1016/j.compgeo.2021.104199.
850 URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compgeo.2021.104199>
- 851 [24] S. A. R. C. Mariotti, P. Heinrich, Numerical simulation of sub-
852 marine landslides and their hydraulic effects, *Journal of Wa-*
853 *terway, Port, Coastal, and Ocean Engineering* 123 (4) (1997).
854 doi:[https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-950X\(1997\)123:4\(149\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-950X(1997)123:4(149)).
- 855 [25] A. Alsardi, A. Yerro, Runout Modeling of Earthquake-Triggered
856 Landslides with the Material Point Method, pp. 21–31.
857 arXiv:<https://ascelibrary.org/doi/pdf/10.1061/9780784483428.003>,
858 doi:10.1061/9780784483428.003.
859 URL <https://ascelibrary.org/doi/abs/10.1061/9780784483428.003>
- 860 [26] H. N., O. A., B. H. H., R. P., R. Fukagawa, Seismic slope failure mod-
861 elling using the mesh-free sph method, *International Journal of Geomate*
862 (2013) 660–665.
- 863 [27] T. Bhandari, F. Hamad, C. Moormann, K. Sharma,
864 B. Westrich, Numerical modelling of seismic slope failure us-
865 ing mpm, *Computers and Geotechnics* 75 (2016) 126–134.
866 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compgeo.2016.01.017>.
867 URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0266352X16000264>
- 868 [28] D. Muir Wood, *Soil behaviour and critical state soil mechanics*, Cam-
869 bridge University Press, United Kingdom, 1990.
- 870 [29] D. Drumheller, On theories for reacting immiscible mixtures, *Inter-*
871 *national Journal of Engineering Science* 38 (3) (2000) 347 – 382.
872 doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0020-7225\(99\)00047-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0020-7225(99)00047-6).
873 URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0020722599000476>
- 874 [30] S. Hassanizadeh, Derivation of basic equations of mass transport in
875 porous media, part1: Macroscopic balance laws, *Advances in Wa-*
876 *ter Resources* 9 (1986) 196–206. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/0309-](https://doi.org/10.1016/0309-1708(86)90024-2)
877 [1708\(86\)90024-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0309-1708(86)90024-2).